

THE INFLUENCE OF ANGIOTENSIN II RECEPTOR ANTAGONISTS ON THE COURSE OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE IN INDIVIDUALS HYPERTENSION DISEASE

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Introduction. Currently, ARA drugs have become very widely used in the treatment of chronic heart failure. The use of losartan at a dose of 150 mg/ day significantly reduces the risk of death and hospitalization in patients with CHF. According to the national recommendations of VNOK and OSHF for the diagnosis and treatment of CHF, if it is appropriate to use ARB drugs for the treatment of CHF, by reducing preload and afterload, LV systolic and diastolic function improves, and the ejection fraction increases. In the treatment of patients with hypertension, the blood pressure value should be less than 140/90 mmHg, which is its target level. If the prescribed therapy is well tolerated, it is advisable to reduce blood pressure to lower values. In patients at high and very high risk of SSO, blood pressure should be lowered to 140/90 mmHg. or less within 4 weeks. In the future, if well tolerated, it is recommended to reduce blood pressure to 130/80 mmHg. st. and less. In patients with coronary artery disease, the blood pressure level should be reduced to the target value of 130/85 mmHg. In patients with diabetes and/or kidney disease, the target BP level should be less than 130/85 mmHg. The emergence of the second class of RAAS blockers – selective antagonists of receptors for ATII – occurred after the strengthening of ACE in-the-line treatment of decompensation. Given the absolute indications for prescribing ACE inhibitions to all patients with CHF, it was impossible to organize placebo-controlled trials with ARA in the "era of ACEIs", which made it difficult to assess the true capabilities of drugs of this class in decompensated patients. Although it is necessary to note the "signature" feature of drugs of this class - excellent tolerability with a minimum of side effects. In addition, ARAs are extremely rare in causing cough and are routinely recommended for the treatment of CHF in ACEI intolerance (as indicated in these guidelines). At the initial stage, the first APA losartan was directly compared with the reference ACE formula, captopril, in order to prove the advantages of a new class of RAAS blockers on mortality and morbidity in patients with CHF, but the hypothesis about the possible benefits of ARA in the treatment of CHF was not confirmed. Use of angiotensin receptor antagonists II, by reducing preload and afterload, lead to a decrease in pressure in the chambers of the heart and, as a result, the myocardial oxygen demand decreases and the diastolic and systolic function of the left ventricle improves.

Purpose of the study. To evaluate the effectiveness of combined angiotensin receptor antagonists II for the treatment of chronic heart failure in patients with hypertension.

Key words: chronic heart failure, angiotensin receptor antagonists II, echocardiography, atrial fibrillation, potassium level.

Materials and methods. We examined 46 patients with hypertension complicated by stage B CHF (NYHA III FC) and atrial fibrillation.

The study was conducted on the basis of the therapeutic department of the Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center. All patients received combination therapy with digoxin in a daily dose of 0.25 mg, intravenous infusion of potassium magnesium aspartate 250 ml,

veroshpiron in a daily dose of 100 mg in combination with losartan in a daily dose of 100 mg. All patients underwent echocardiography, ECG and also determination of plasma potassium concentration .

Research results . According to the results of our study, before the use of traditional therapy in 23 patients (50%), according to echocardiography, EF was below 32%, and the potassium level was below 3.6 mmol /l. The ECG of almost all patients showed a tachysystolic form of atrial fibrillation with a heart rate of 110-150 beats per minute. Against the background of the above combination therapy, on the 3rd day the clinical condition of the patients improved . With repeated echocardiography, global contractility of the left ventricle increased (EF increased by 57%), signs of CHF decreased: swelling in the lower extremities subsided, shortness of breath and the number of moist rales in the lungs decreased. The tachysystolic form of atrial fibrillation transformed into a normosystolic form with a heart rate of 76-85 beats per minute. In both observed groups, ACE therapy in combination with indapamide II FC (NYHA) and APA in combination with indapamide FC III (NYHA) reduced the severity of dyspnea, signs of congestion in the pulmonary circulation, and swelling in the legs decreased significantly. The frequency of complaints about heart failures has decreased, the number of patients with a forced position has decreased, the number of patients with a forced position has decreased, and the number of patients with swelling of the cervical veins has decreased. The incidence of lung wheezing decreased by more than 80% in patients with FC III (NYHA). The second group included 35 patients with hypertension and LV dysfunction who received the angiotensin II receptor (ARA) blocker losartan 50 mg/day in combination with ACEI, capoten 12.5 mg/day and indapamide 1.5 mg/day. In all patients included in this group, signs of CHF III FC (NYHA) were diagnosed as a complication of hypertension. Mean systolic blood pressure values at baseline. 180 ± 18.3 mmHg Diastolic blood pressure (DBP) was. 9.5 ± 8.5 mmHg Glomerular filtration rate (GFR) before therapy was 98 ml/min, with signs of oliguria (650 ml per day). Against the background of the above therapy with a moderately high degree of efficacy, GFR increased to 110 ml/min.

Conclusions: Thus , it should be noted that it is the combined use of losartan in a daily dose of 100 mg for the treatment of CHF that will improve the clinical condition of patients, as well as prevent further complications of this disease. The combination of ACE inhibitors, ARA and indapamide significantly improves the clinical course of CHF and reduces the severity of decompensation symptoms (by 53%). The combination of ACEI, ARA and indapamide improves the contractile function of the heart and increases the ejection fraction of the left ventricle. (by 10.7%) The efficacy of the combined use of ARA and indopamide increases especially in patients with CHF III FC (NYHA). The combined use of ACE inhibitors and APA blockers leads to an increase in GFR, an increase in urine output, and a decrease in edematous syndrome.

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